

Synergistic in-vitro Antimicrobial Activities of Combined Methanol Stem Bark Extracts of *Morinda lucida* and *Pterocarpus santalinoides* Against Clinical Isolates from Diabetic Foot Ulcers

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ABSTRACT.

Background: The past few decades have shown a rising interest in research towards the development of newer antimicrobials to help curtail emerging multiple drug-resistant microbes that are posing a serious global health risk to the populace. **Objectives:** To assess the antimicrobial effects of methanol stem bark extracts from *M. lucida* and *P. santalinoides* on multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria isolated from diabetic foot ulcers. **Materials and Methods** The bacterial isolates, obtained from patients at University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu, were tested for antibiotic resistance. Antimicrobial activities of the methanol stem bark extracts were tested using the agar well diffusion test. The minimum inhibitory concentration and fractional inhibitory concentration were done using the Checker-board micro-titration method and the fractional inhibitory concentration index calculated. The time-kill assay was done to confirm synergistic and bactericidal activity using the MIC's obtained. **Results:** Phytochemical analysis revealed that it contained tannin, alkaloids, phenol, terpenoids, saponin, and glycosides. Antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed that the combined extracts were active against the MDR microbial isolates tested with varying inhibitory zone diameter which ranged between 25 and 37mm. The fractional inhibitory concentration index of the combination showed synergism (0.18-0.35mm). The time-kill assay confirmed the synergistic and bactericidal activity by a 3log 10 CFU/mL decrease in the number of viable cells within 6 hours of incubation. **Conclusion:** The combination of *M. lucida* and *P. santalinoides* methanol stem bark extracts could be a promising treatment for diabetic wound infections caused by MDR bacteria,

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including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

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INTRODUCTION

Herbal plants have been found to contain numerous phytochemicals that contribute to their therapeutic potentials both in-vivo and in-vitro.[1] The beneficial properties of medicinal plants are attributed to the secondary metabolites they contain.[2] In ethnomedicine, *M. lucida* is considered a highly important plant due to its use in managing various infections and diseases.[3] The stem bark reveals a bright yellow colour when cut. *Pterocarpus santalinoides* is traditionally used in folklore medicine to promote wound healing.[4] Combining plants offers several advantages over monotherapy, including enhancing the effectiveness of other antimicrobial agents, thereby reducing the required dosage, decreasing toxicity, minimising adverse reactions, targeting multiple sites, reducing the development of multi-drug resistance (MDR), and overcoming MDR organisms. [5]

Diabetic foot ulcers are the most dreaded, impediment of diabetes. [6] It is a latent life-threatening complication of diabetic patients. [7] When these ulcers get infected by microbes, it makes the wound difficult to heal. The prolonged use of antimicrobials to clean and treat them, exposes the infecting pathogen to the development of multiple drug resistance, giving the patient a greater chance of amputation. The pathogens usually associated with diabetic foot ulcers are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus spp*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterococcus spp*, *Escherichia coli*. The contamination is mostly poly-microbial giving rise to a greater spread of tissue degeneration.

The increase of multiple drug-resistant pathogens has led to treatment failures and overstay in hospital and makes treatment very challenging. There is an urgent need to search for alternative antimicrobials agents that will be effective, safe and readily available that will help to overcome/eliminate multiple drug resistant microorganisms. This study

aimed to evaluate the in-vitro synergistic antimicrobial effects of a poly-herbal mixture of methanol stem bark extracts from *Morinda lucida* and *Pterocarpus santalinoides* against multi-drug resistant bacteria isolated from diabetic foot ulcers. The objectives were to analyze the phytochemical components, assess the inhibition zones of the individual and combined extracts, and determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), fractional inhibitory concentration (FIC), fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI), and time-kill assay of the synergistic combinations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The stem bark of *P. santalinoides* and *M. lucida* was collected from trees in the family garden at the University of Nigeria Enugu Campus senior staff quarters. The plants were authenticated and identified by Mr. Felix Nwafor, an expert botanist from the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. A voucher specimen number was assigned, and the specimen was deposited in the herbarium. The bark was thoroughly washed multiple times with clean water, cut into small pieces to facilitate drying and grinding, shade-dried, pulverized into powder, and stored in a clean, sterile container (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1: Stem bark of *Morinda lucida*

Figure 2: Stem bark of *Pterocarpus santalinoides*.
Extraction of the Stem bark

Cold maceration was used to extract the stem-bark extracts. Each pulverized stem-bark weighing one kilogram was mixed with 5L of 95% methanol with constant shaking for 48 hours. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated *in-vacuo* at 40°C. The sterility of the extract was done by incubating at 37°C on Mueller Hinton agar

Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical constituents of the stem barks were assessed to determine the phytochemical constituents and this was done using standard methods as described by.[8]

Antimicrobial in-vitro activity

The multiple drug-resistant bacteria isolates tested were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antimicrobial resistance profile and presence of genes were determined before use. Bacterial cell suspension was made from a 24-hour fresh culture and standardized to 0.5 McFarland standard.

The antibacterial activity of the extracts singly and in combination was done using the agar well diffusion method described by. [9] The standardized cell suspension was evenly spread on Mueller Hinton agar and allowed to dry for 15 minutes and 5 wells were created on the agar and 0.5mL of each stem-bark and the poly-herbal combination was added in the wells with positive and negative controls. The positive control is levofloxacin (0.05mg/ml) and DMSO is the negative control. They were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. This was done in triplicate and the zones of inhibition around each well were recorded in mm. The result is expressed as the mean of the three readings.

A checkerboard was used to evaluate the minimum inhibitory concentration and synergistic antimicrobial combinations of stem bark of both plant extracts against the test isolates using the agar diffusion method by calculating the fractional inhibitory concentration index method of. [10, 11]. A 96 micro-titration well was filled with 1.5mL of Muller Hilton broth, 100µL of *Pterocarpus santalinoides* added to the first row on the X-axis and serially diluted, and 100µL of *M.*

lucida extract added to the first row on the Y-axis and it was serially diluted 100µL of standardized bacterial inoculums properly vortexed and added into the 96 wells. The plate was incubated overnight at 37°C. The MIC was determined by checking for the presence of bacteria by adding 20µL of 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) into the wells and then incubating for an extra one hour The least concentration that did not produce a red colour signifying the absence of bacteria was regarded as the MIC. [8]

The fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI) is used to interoperate antimicrobial combination= ≤ 0.5 = synergism; $0.51 < FICI \leq 4.0$ = indifferent FICI > 4.0 = antagonistic and was calculated using the equation described by. [12]

$$FICA = \frac{(\text{MIC of } Pterocarpus \text{ santalinoides and } Morinda \text{ lucida in combination})}{(\text{MIC } Pterocarpus \text{ santalinoides alone})}$$

$$FICB = \frac{(\text{MIC-of } Pterocarpus \text{ santalinoides and } Morinda \text{ lucida in combination})}{(\text{MIC } Morinda \text{ lucida alone})}$$

$$FICI = FICA + FICB$$

Time-kill assay for bactericidal and synergistic testing

The bacteriostatic concentration obtained was used to confirm the bactericidal action. This was done using the methods of. [12, 13]. This was assessed at 2×MIC and 3×MIC with eighty microliters of the extract. It was added to the test tube containing 1000 µL of Muller Hilton broth and 20 µL of each standardized bacteria inoculum... A 100 µL of the combination was removed every 2 hours for 12 hours and diluted out 1 in 10. A 10 µL of it was cultured on Muller Hilton agar. The plate count was done after overnight incubation and the graph of logarithm of number of colonies in cfu/mL and time of incubation was plotted. Bactericidal activity is said to occur when the activity is greater than ≥ 2 log₁₀ CFU/mL fold reduction in the initial inoculums. [14]

Statistical Analysis

The results were expressed as the mean of three replicates. The significance level was set at $p \leq 0.05$. Data obtained were statistically analyzed using one-way Analysis of Variance ANOVA.

RESULTS

The percentage yield of *M.lucida* stem bark extract was (26.3%) while that of *P.santalinoides* is (21.43%). The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, saponins, terpenes, and flavonoids as shown in table 1.

The mean inhibition zone for *M. lucida* ranged from 14 to 26mm at a concentration of 100mg/mL, meeting the CLSI-recommended inhibition zones for the tested isolates. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most sensitive, while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the least sensitive. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was 6.25mg/mL for *S. aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, and 12.5mg/mL for the other isolates. *P. santalinoides* produced inhibition zones between 14 and 23mm, with an MIC of 25mg/mL for all isolates. *S. aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *E. coli* were the most sensitive to this extract. Overall, *M. lucida* stem bark extract showed stronger inhibition zones compared to *P. santalinoides* against the tested isolates.

The inhibition zone diameter of the poly-herbal stem bark combination range between 25 - 37 mm as shown in Table 3 . The combined plant extracts had a higher zone of inhibition compared to the extracts when used singly. The combination had a better effect on *P.mirabilis*, and *E. coli* and the least on *Klebsiella pneumonia* based on the zones of inhibition diameter produced

The FICI values for synergism ranged from 0.18 to 0.37, as indicated in Table 4. The combination showed the strongest synergistic effect against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, followed by *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, with *Proteus mirabilis* exhibiting the least synergism.

The time-kill assay of the antimicrobial combination (Figure 3) showed the bactericidal activities of the plant combination at 2×MIC and 3×MIC. At the 2×MIC it showed a $\geq 3 \log_{10}$ reduction in the number of viable cells within 6 hours of incubation while at 3×MIC the number of viable cells reduced drastically before 4 hours of incubation and there was no re-growth observed signifying a powerful bactericidal activity and synergy between the two combination. There was a gross increase in the number of viable cells in the control as the time of incubation increased.

Table 1: Phytochemical analysis of *M.lucida* and *P. santalinoides* methanol stem bark extract

Plant	Saponins	Tannins	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Phenols	Steroids	Terpenoids	Glycosides
<i>Pterocarpus santalinoides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Morinda lucida</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Key: + present

Table 2: Mean inhibition zone diameter (mm) and MIC of *Morinda lucida* and *Pterocarpus santalinoides*.

Bacteria Isolate	<i>Morinda lucida</i>					<i>Pterocarpus santalinoides</i>						
	Zone Of Inhibition Diameter (mm)=[';';'';					MIC mg/mL	Zone Of Inhibition Diameter (mm)					MIC mg/mL
	400	200	100	50	25		400	200	100	50	25	
<i>S. aureus</i>	26.00 ±0.2	24.00 ±0.7	22.00 ±0.0	20.00 ±0.1	18.00 ±0.9	6.25	23.00 ±0.1	21.00 ±0.8	19.00 ±0.5	18.00 ±0.2	16.00 ±0.9	25.00

<i>K. pneumonia</i>	23.00 ±0.9	21.00 ±0.4	20.00 ±0.3	19.00 ±0.0	16.00± 0.6	12. 5	21. 00±0. 6	19. .00±0. 3	17.00 ±0.4	15.00 ±0.8	14.00± 0.5	25. 00
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	21.00 ±0.2	20.00 ±0.0	19.00 ±0.1	17.00 ±0.3	14.00± 0.7	12. 5	21.00 ±0.2	20.00 ±0.	19.00 ±0.4	17.00 ±0.5	14.00± 0.9	25. 00
<i>E. coli</i>	23.00 ±0.4	21.00 ±0.8	20.00 ±0.3	18.00 ±0.9	17.00± 0.4	6.2 5	23.00 ±0.2	21.00 ±0.8	20.00 ±0.5	18.00 ±0.9	15.00± 0.0	25. 00
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	23.00 ±0.0	22.00 ±0.2	21.00 ±0.7	19.00 ±0.3	15.00± 0.6	12. 5	23.00 ±0.7	21.00 ±0.0	19.00 ±0.3	17.00 ±0.4	14.00± 0.6	25. 00

Table 3: Mean inhibition zone diameter (mm) of polyherbal combination of *Morinda lucida* and *Pterocarpus santalinoides*

Concentration of extract combination at 1:1 ratio (mg/mL)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>
400	36.00±0.02	35.000±0.06	35.000±0.01	37.000±0.02	37.000±0.00
200	34.000±0.07	34.000±0.09	34.000±0.00	33.000±0.05	34.000±0.023
100	32.000±0.04	32.000±0.04	31.000±0.08	33.000±0.04	32.000±0.04
50	29.000±0.03	28.000±0.04	28.000±0.03	29.000±0.01	29.000±0.08
25	27.000±0.01	25.000±0.02	25.000±0.09	27.000±0.06	26.000±0.02
Levofloxacin 0.005mg/ml	40.00±0.0	40.00±0.0	39.00±0.0	41.00±0.0	40.00±0.0

Table 4: Fractional Inhibitory Concentration Index of the polyherbal combination of *Morinda lucida* and *Pterocarpus santalinoides* stem bark extract against the multiple drug resistant bacteria isolates tested

Test Isolates	MIC of Combination Mg/MI	FIC _A	FIC _B	FICI	Interpretation
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	3.12	0.25	0.12	0.37	Synergy
<i>S. aureus</i>	1.56	0.25	0.06	0.31	Synergy
<i>K.pneumonia</i>	1.56	0.12	0.06	0.18	Synergy
<i>E. coli</i>	1.56	0.25	0.06	0.18	Synergy
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	1.56	0.12	0.06	0.18	Synergy

Figure 3 : Time kill assay curve for Poly-herbal Combination of *M.lucida* and *P.santalinoides* stem bark extract against multiple drug resistance Isolates from Diabetic Foot Ulcers at 2X and 3 X MIC.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical constituents obtained in this study is in agreement with similar studies earlier conducted by. [15, 16] These phytochemicals suggested that the extract and its metabolite have anti-microbial activities against several human pathogens since they contain diverse phytochemical compounds. They have been associated with various bioactive elements that possess medical properties. [17]

Bacteria resistance to multiple classes of antimicrobials is among the major global threats yearly. [18.] Discovering alternative antimicrobials that are effective, safe, and pocket-friendly is the goal of biomedical research. The stem bark of *P.santalinoides* and *M.lucida* were evaluated for in-vitro antimicrobial activities against multiple drug-resistance isolates from diabetic foot ulcers. From Table 2, the zones of inhibition of both plants indicate they are both sensitive to the multiple drug resistance isolates. This is in line with the study of.[19, 20]where the stem bark of *M.lucida* had activity against all the tested isolates in a concentration-dependent manner. This explains its use by traditional healers in the treatment of numerous infections and diseases.

The antimicrobial activities of the stem bark polyherbal combination combined at the ratio of 1:1 showed very high inhibition zone diameter which is far greater than the CLSI zones of inhibition zone diameter indicating they are very sensitive to the isolates as shown in table 4. The antimicrobial potential of the poly-herbal combination could be a result of the phytochemicals working in synergy with each other to strengthen their effect as a pool of substances working as multiple drugs. [21] Therefore, drug combination can help produce a higher therapeutic selective response than monotherapy. [22] Antimicrobial combination helps to reduce the danger of cross-resistance and prevent overlapping pathways making it an optional and encouraging treatment option.[21]

The plant extract working in synergism helps in the reduction of the MIC, reducing the amount of antimicrobial consumed. [23] This is similar to our work where the MIC of the extracts in combination is far much lower than the individual MICs. When plant extract combinations work in synergy they work as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial. [24]

A checkerboard technique was used to calculate the fractional inhibitory concentration index to determine the synergistic status of the combination. It is advisable to determine the synergistic status of any drug combination before administering it because most combinations do not produce synergy. The fractional inhibitory concentration index of the plant extract combination showed that they produced synergistic activities against the multiple drug resistance isolates. An antimicrobial combination that shows synergism is indicative that both extracts have different modes of action. [25] The synergistic interaction helps cell mediators to improve antimicrobial activity, improve the biochemical pathways, and adjust microbial enzymes. [26] Due to the paucity of information on the combination of this unique combination comparison of results becomes very difficult. Phenol has been linked to the synergistic actions of plant combination as has been documented to help in the reduction of 1 MIC of antibiotics. [27]

A greater than $\geq 3\log_{10}$ decrease in the number of viable cells at 3X MIC and 2X MIC before 4 hours and 6-8 hours respectively as seen in Fig 3 is an indication that it is a good bactericidal agent. A good bactericidal agent should produce a lethal dose of 90% in 6 hours which is equal to 99% cell death. [28] The time-kill assay curve confirms the bactericidal and synergistic interaction of both stem-bark extract combinations against the multiple drug resistance isolates from diabetic foot ulcers. [29]

The manuscript was a novel work that dealt with actual confirmation of synergism which most works on plant combination have not been able to establish. Determining the time-kill assay curve to confirm the synergism and bactericidal effect was another landmark achievement in the study which is not common in numerous plant combination works. Not all plant combinations produce synergistic effects. The limitation was the polyherbal combination was not tested on wider range of microorganisms.

CONCLUSION

M. lucida and *P. santalinoides* combination methanol stem bark extracts revealed the antimicrobial activities as shown. Very high inhibition zone of diameter against all the MDR isolates. The FICI of *P. santalinoides* and *M. lucida*

in combination indicates the combinations had a synergistic effect. The general outcome of this work gives scientific backup to their native usage in the treatment of wound infections.

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Author contribution

ANO, EIB and APU conceptualized and designed the study. ANO and OSU contributed to implementation of the project and revision of the manuscript. All authors were involved in the writing and revision of the manuscript. The authors read, approved the final manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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Ethical Approval

Ethical permission to carry out this work was obtained from the Ethics Committee College of Medicine University of Nigeria.

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